

Research Article

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Assessment of Oil Spill Dispersion and Weathering Processes in Saronic Gulf

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Abstract

An operational oil spill model is applied to assess the dispersive properties of oil and reveal the relative magnitude of weathering processes following an accidental spill near the main Greek harbor of Piraeus, situated within Saronic Gulf. We conduct numerical simulations using the OpenOil transport and fate numerical model, a subclass of the Open Drift open-source trajectory framework. This model will incorporate algorithms encompassing various physical processes, including oil entrainment, vertical mixing, oil resurfacing, and oil emulsification. The oil dispersion model is coupled with real-time met-ocean forecasts obtained from Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS). The primary focus of the simulation results will be on assessing the impact of speed, direction, and distance covered, driven by the background flow field, on the horizontal spreading of particles. Additionally, the study will analyze the evolution of oil mass balance and properties over time. The research will commence with the operational coupling of OpenOil with winds derived from the Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) model. Subsequently, enhancements are made in the parameterization of oil weathering processes, such as biodegradation, with the aim of improving the accuracy of the model in capturing the fate and behavior of spilled oil over time. These refinements are expected to yield valuable insights into the management and mitigation of oil spill incidents in marine environments, particularly in regions like Saronic Gulf, characterized by high maritime traffic and potential environmental vulnerability.

Keywords: Oil spill; Weathering processes; OpenOil; WRF; Saronic Gulf; Numerical simulations

Introduction

A study by [1] shows that rising global demand and declining land-based oil reserves have led to a major increase in offshore oil and gas production since the 1990s. At the same time, improvements in oil transport—such as supertankers and large pipeline networks—have helped move oil across oceans more efficiently. However, this

growth also increases the risk of oil spills, which can seriously harm marine life and have long-lasting environmental, social, and economic impacts.

Oil spills can happen in many ways: from natural leaks, oil transport, drilling, or accidents involving ships, pipelines, or rigs.

Smaller spills are usually easier to manage, but large spills are much harder to control and more damaging. Even though recent studies suggest a drop in major spills (see Table 1 on Mediterranean incidents), the public often focuses on big disasters and overlooks the many smaller spills that happen daily [2]. According to ITOFF and the European Space Agency, more than 80% of oil spill incidents

since 1970 have been small (under 7 tons). Still, around 250,000 tons of oil are lost each year during ship operations, with another 120,000 tons spilled near refineries and terminals. Unfortunately, data on accidental spills is often missing or incomplete, highlighting the urgent need for better spill detection and monitoring systems.

Table 1: Recorded incidents in the Mediterranean Sea.

Date	Location	Oil spill (tn)
15-May-66	Sardinia	6,000
01-Nov-70	Sicily	15,000
11-Jun-72	Greece	37,000
25-Apr-76	Algeria	31,000
30-Jun-76	Greece	15,000
10-Aug-77	Bosporus Strait, Turkey	20,000
25-Dec-78	Turkey	10,000
02-Mar-79	Crete	16,000
15-Nov-79	Bosporus Strait, Turkey	64,000
23-Feb-80	Navarino Bay, Greece	100,000
29-Dec-80	Algeria	37,000
29-Mar-81	Corsica	12,200
11-Apr-91	Genoa	144,000
30-Dec-00	Morocco	9,900
14-Jul-06	Lebanon	15,000 – 30,000
10-Sep-17	Piraeus, Greece	700 – 2,500
11-Feb-21	Lebanon	unknown
Summary		
17 cases	Mediterranean Basin	~ 540,000

Oil pollution doesn't just affect the sea surface-it can also reach deeper waters, worsening its environmental impact. As oil drilling moves into deeper areas and pipelines are built at greater depths, the risk of accidents like blowouts and leaks increases [3]. Major deep-water spills include the 2010 Deepwater Horizon disaster in the Gulf of Mexico, which released an estimated 492,000 to 627,000 tons of oil, and the 2011 Penglai 19-3 spill in China's Bohai Sea, which released about 200 tons [4].

How an oil spill spreads and changes in the ocean depends on many interacting physical, chemical, and biological processes. Key factors include the type of oil, ocean conditions (like wind, waves, and currents), and how the oil is released-suddenly or continuously, at the surface or from deep underwater. Oil undergoes weathering processes such as spreading, evaporation, emulsification, dissolution, photo-oxidation, biodegradation, and settling. These, along with physical forces like mixing, transport, and resurfacing, determine how the spill moves and how long its effects last [5].

When oil is released into the sea, it quickly spreads into a thin layer on the surface [6]. Oil spill models use this spreading behavior to estimate the thickness or surface area of the slick, which is key

for predicting how the oil will move and change. The speed and extent of spreading depend on factors like water temperature, and the oil's viscosity and density [7]. Evaporation happens when the lighter parts of the oil turn into gas and escape into the air-usually within a few hours-reducing the spill's toxicity [8]. Emulsification occurs when waves mix water into the oil, forming a thick, sticky "mousse." Thicker oils tend to form more mousse, which slows evaporation [9]. Dissolution allows oil to mix into the water, either from the surface or from small droplets. Although both evaporation and dissolution remove oil, evaporation usually happens faster and affects more of the spill [10]. Biodegradation, once thought to take months, can now begin within a week in some cases, as seen in the Deepwater Horizon spill [11, 12]. Photo-oxidation occurs when sunlight chemically alters the oil, producing water-soluble compounds [12]. Sedimentation happens when oil droplets sink due to increased density or by being eaten and excreted by marine organisms [13].

The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model stands as a leading-edge numerical weather prediction and regional atmospheric model, crafted for both research and operational

applications. Developed through a collaborative effort among various agencies and institutions, including National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the Department of Defense, and university researchers, WRF embodies a versatile and efficient codebase adaptable to diverse computing environments. Its modular structure and wide array of physics and dynamics options make it suitable for an extensive range of applications, from real-time weather forecasting to regional climate simulations and air quality modeling. With its widespread adoption globally, WRF continues to serve as a vital tool for advancing our understanding and prediction of mesoscale weather phenomena [14].

Several studies have used the WRF model to better understand wind patterns and improve weather forecasting in coastal and offshore regions. For example, [15] used WRF to study wind behavior over the eastern Mediterranean and compared model outputs with satellite data from Envisat ASAR. This helped them analyze complex wind features like mountain lee waves. [16] showed that combining WRF data with satellite observations improved alignment with buoy measurements, aiding wind energy planning along the Iberian coast. [17] created detailed wind records (SeaWind I and II) using WRF for the Mediterranean, refining the model through sensitivity tests and validating results with buoys and satellite data. [18] tested eight WRF setups across the Northern Sahara and Mediterranean, finding that grid nudging improved wind and temperature predictions [19] used WRF to study wind energy potential off the coast of Southern Brazil, finding good agreement with the Blended Sea Winds product. [20] applied WRF to examine weather changes caused by the 2010 Deepwater Horizon oil spill, underlining the importance of such modeling for cleanup safety and environmental management.

OpenDrift is an open-source, Python-based modeling tool developed by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute for simulating how particles move in air or water [21]. Its flexible design allows it to be used in oil spill tracking, search and rescue, marine biology, and more. [22] used OpenDrift with high-resolution data to study the 2010 Deepwater Horizon oil spill. They found that river outflows had a major impact on where and how much oil reached shore, showing the importance of including river fronts in oil spill models. [23] used OpenDrift to study oil movement over six years, focusing on how ocean currents like the Loop Current affect oil transport in the Straits of Florida. [24] applied OpenDrift with a detailed ocean model in New Zealand's Bay of Plenty. Using data from 2003–2004, the model successfully reproduced coastal currents and showed that local winds strongly influenced nearshore movement, especially through wind-driven upwelling in certain areas.

This study is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines the methodology, including a description of the Saronic Gulf study area, an overview of the OpenOil model, integration of real-time weather and ocean data, and details of the simulation setup. Section 3 presents the results, covering three WRF spatial resolution scenarios, the influence of biodegradation, and changes in oil mass and properties. Section 4 provides conclusions, highlights key findings, and offers recommendations for future research and

model improvements.

Methodology

The methodology section starts with an introduction to the OpenOil model and its requirements. It then provides an overview of the Saronic Gulf, followed by a discussion of the physical properties, governing equations, and components. Finally, it outlines the simulation setup and experiment parameters.

OpenOil model and its elements

This analysis examines a hypothetical oil spill near the major Greek harbor of Piraeus in the Saronic Gulf. The simulation uses the OpenOil model, which combines oil spill transport and weathering with real-time meteorological and oceanographic data. OpenOil is part of the open Drift framework [21] and models oil as individual particles with specific properties like mass, viscosity, and density, known as Lagrangian elements.

The movement of each oil particle is affected by factors such as currents, wind, and Stokes drift, along with random walk models to simulate diffusion from turbulence. The model also accounts for physical processes like wave entrainment [25], turbulence-driven vertical mixing [26], oil resurfacing due to buoyancy [27], and emulsification [28]. Oil resurfacing is based on oil density and droplet size, with sinking velocity determined by Stokes' Law, making the model sensitive to the initial oil droplet size distribution [22].

Physical OpenOil parameters

The current simulations incorporate a comprehensive understanding of various physical processes governing oil transport. These include (a) horizontal transport, which accounts for ambient horizontal currents, the impact of wave-induced Stokes drift, and the wind drift. (b) Vertical transport and mixing are also crucial factors, involving phenomena such as waves breaking in the open sea, particles resurfacing due to buoyancy, and their movement under vertical turbulence.

Horizontal transport

Oil elements are subject to advection by currents, wind, and waves, which collectively influence their horizontal motion. Whether submerged or at the surface, oil particles follow the ambient current, experience wind drift – crucial for their horizontal movement – which typically ranges from approximately 1% to 6% of the surface wind speed, often around 3%. Additionally, they are affected by the surface Stokes drift, with its profile calculated by [29] based on the Phillips spectrum.

Vertical transport

A) Wave entrainment: Wave entrainment involves repositioning oil droplets from the surface slick into the water column, influenced by wave energy, oil properties, and environmental conditions [30]. Recent studies have parameterized wave entrainment, considering oil slick characteristics, water density, and energy from breaking waves [31]. The rate of oil entrainment, Q , is described by Equation (1):

$$Q = 4.604 \times 10^{-10} W_e^{1.805} Oh^{-1.023} F_{bw} \quad (1)$$

where, W_e (Weber number) and Oh (Ohnesorge number) represent the balance of inertial, surface tension, and viscous forces, and F_{bw} is the fraction of the sea surface with breaking waves, as discussed in Li et al. (2017) and [32].

B) Oil droplet distribution: Wave entrainment affects the size distribution of oil droplets within the water column. Droplets range from 1 μm to 1 mm, with size distributions described by number or volume distributions [33]. The volume distribution, often used in modeling, is represented by the median droplet diameter D_{50}^v (Eq. 2):

$$D_{50}^v = d_o r_e (1 + 100h)^p W_e^q \quad (2)$$

where, d_o is the Rayleigh–Taylor instability maximum diameter, $r_e = 1.791$, $\rho = 0.46$, and $q = -0.518$ are empirical coefficients [32]. The size distribution follows a log-normal pattern and varies with weather and emulsification rates [22].

C) Oil resurfacing: Buoyancy affects the movement of oil droplets, with the terminal velocity dependent on droplet size and density differences between oil and water [34]. The vertical terminal velocity w is given by equation (3):

$$w(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{2g(1-\bar{\rho})}{9\nu} r^2 & \text{if } Re \leq 50 \\ \sqrt{\frac{16}{3} g(1-\bar{\rho})} r & \text{if } Re > 50 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where, r is the droplet radius, g is the gravity acceleration,

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho_{oil}}{\rho_{water}}$$

ρ_{oil} and ρ_{water} is the oil and water density, respectively, ν is the kinematic water viscosity and $Re = \frac{2rw}{\nu}$ is the droplet Reynolds number.

D) Turbulent mixing: Turbulent mixing redistributes oil droplets vertically, influenced by wind speed, current shear, stratification, and wave energy dissipation. The intensity of turbulent mixing is characterized by a vertical eddy diffusivity coefficient $K(z)$ [35]. This coefficient governs turbulent diffusion, described by Equation 4:

$$\Delta z = K'(z_n) \Delta t + R \sqrt{\frac{2}{r} K \left(z_n + \frac{K'(z_n) \Delta t}{2} \right) \Delta t} \quad (4)$$

where, $\Delta z = z_{n+1} - z_n$ is the vertical displacement, $K'(z_n)$ is the derivative of the eddy diffusivity coefficient, $K(z)$ with respect to the vertical coordinate z , and R is a random process with a mean $\mu_{<R^2>} = 0$ and a standard deviation $\sigma_{<R^2>} = r$ [36].

Oil weathering processes

OpenOil uses advanced models for oil weathering, including

evaporation and emulsification, based on oil properties from the Oil Library (ADIOS) software by NOAA. Evaporation rates vary by oil type and are influenced by factors like wind speed. Some oils can evaporate completely in a few hours, while others may not evaporate at all. Lighter oils tend to evaporate faster, with 20-40% evaporating in the first 6-12 hours [34]. Evaporation and emulsification affect oil density, viscosity, and oil-water interfacial tension, which in turn influence droplet size distribution [22].

A) Evaporation: Regarding oil evaporation, OpenOil adapts its treatment based on the conditions of the oil slick [37]. Under calm conditions where the oil forms a smooth surface, evaporation is modeled using Mackay's analytical method [38]. However, under rough weather conditions, a more complex approach is employed (ADIOS2), which utilizes a pseudo-component evaporation model [39]. In this model, crude oils and refined products are represented as a small number of discrete, non-interacting components, each with its own vapor pressure. The evaporation rate for each component is determined by factors such as wind speed, slick thickness, and the molar fraction and volume of the component. The relative molar volume of each component is estimated based on empirical correlations with the boiling point of alkanes, allowing for accurate calculation of vapor pressures using Antoine's equation [40].

B) Emulsification: While evaporation reduces the volume of the surface slick, emulsification increases it. In a manner similar to evaporation, the emulsification rate according to ADIOS1 is governed by a simple first-order rate law proposed by [41]. This law estimates the rate of change of water content in the oil-water emulsion as a function of wind speed, current water fraction, and the maximum water fraction of the emulsion. Emulsification tends to increase the water content over time, with typical values for the emulsification rate constant ranging from 1 to 2 $\mu\text{s}/\text{m}^2$ of the slick surface. As mixing progresses, the droplet size distribution shifts towards smaller droplets while the total water content remains constant [37].

On the other hand, ADIOS2 considers the rate of emulsion formation using a first-order rate law in the interfacial area, rather than water content [42]. This formulation, proposed by Eley et al. [43], describes the rate of change of the interfacial area in terms of an interfacial parameter (k_s), which is sensitive to wave energy. The interfacial area is related to the oil-water interfacial area and the maximum interfacial area, with the water fraction being linked to the interfacial area and the average water droplet diameter.

C) Biodegradation: Biodegradation stands as a pivotal natural process capable of mitigating the environmental repercussions of marine oil spills over the long haul. The rate of biodegradation for oil hinges on several factors including the composition of petroleum hydrocarbons, temperature, microbial species present, and the availability of oxygen and nutrients. The biodegradation algorithm integrated into OpenOil draws from the work of Adcroft et al. [44], asserting that the biological breakdown of oil is primarily influenced by temperature. Specifically, the full biodegradation

period (R^{-1}), measured in days, is determined by the Equation (5):

$$R^{-1} = 12days \times 3^{(20^{\circ}C-T)/10^{\circ}C} \quad (5)$$

where, R^{-1} denotes the time required for oil and T the water temperature, in both dissolved and undissolved phases, to be colonized by bacteria and microorganisms, and for the most resilient compounds within the oil to undergo metabolism.

Study Area and simulation setup

The Saronic Gulf is nested in the west-central Aegean Sea, bordered by the Attica peninsula to the north and east, and the Peloponnese to the southwest. It shares its boundaries with the Aegean Sea to the south and southeast, boasting numerous islands and islets, notably Salamina, Aegina and Hydra, depicted in Fig. 1. Spanning approximately 270 km of coastline, the gulf encompasses a sea surface area of around 2890 km², with an average water depth of roughly 100 meters [45].

Figure 1: Saronic Gulf study area with meteorological stations.

To improve accuracy, the OpenOil model uses atmospheric data from the WRF model and ocean data from the CMEMS database. This combination provides a more realistic simulation of oil spill behavior under different environmental conditions. The WRF model (version 4.3) [46] simulates atmospheric conditions with nested domains: a large-scale domain (25 km resolution), an intermediate domain (5 km), an inner domain (1 km), and a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) domain (200 m resolution). It uses various parameterizations, including the two-moment Morrison scheme for microphysics [47], the RRTMG scheme for radiation [48], the Betts-Miller-Janjic (BMJ) scheme for convection [49], the Mellor-Yamada-Janjic (MYJ) scheme for the Planetary Boundary Layer [50], and the Noah Land model. For higher resolutions (1 km and above), convective and PBL schemes are turned off, as the model can resolve these processes directly. The Global Forecast System (GFS) provides initial and boundary conditions. The LES output frequency is set to 30 seconds, and simulations run for 7 days, with

the LES domain running for only 2 days due to high computational cost. A 6-hour spin-up run is conducted before each simulation. Oceanographic data consists of hydrodynamic conditions and wave data. Hydrodynamic data, including ocean currents, come from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) Mediterranean Sea Physics dataset [51], while wave data is from the CMEMS Mediterranean Sea Waves dataset [52].

Oil properties in OpenOil are sourced from the ADIOS Oil database, which contains data on nearly 1,000 oil types [37]. In this study, crude oil is released near Piraeus Harbor over five days, from February 1 to February 6, 2024. The simulation setup is shown in Figure 2, which includes: (a) surface current speed, and (b) significant wave height (VHM0), all derived from the CMEMS datasets. These variables-current speed and wave height-are key factors in oil dispersion. Figures 2a and 2b show a consistent pattern, indicating that current conditions remained stable throughout the simulation period.

Figure 2: (a) Surface current speed and (b) wave significant height (VHM0) at three different locations within the Saronic Gulf.

The oil type used is “BRENT (AD00187),” with a density of 835.1 kg/m³ and viscosity of 7×10⁻⁶ m²/s at 20°C. A total of 20,000 oil particles are released over a 200 m spill radius, with an initial

oil mass of 167,020 kg (200 m³). Table 2 summarizes the initial simulation conditions.

Table 2: Initial simulation conditions and input datasets.

Condition	Description
Oil spill coordinates	Lon: 23.61o & Lat: 37.92o
Number of particles	20,000
Simulation start time	February 1, 2024
Simulation end time	February 6, 2024
Duration	5 days
Oil type	BRENT (AD00187)
Atmospheric data	Link to data
Hydrodynamic data	Link to data
Wave data	Link to data

Results

This section presents the simulation results. It begins with three WRF simulations using different horizontal resolutions, compared with data from local weather stations. Next, it examines oil weathering with and without biodegradation, showing how the oil's mass balance and properties change over time.

Spatial WRF scenarios

Three WRF simulations were performed using horizontal

resolutions of 5 km, 1 km, and 200 m. The 5 km and 1 km simulations ran for the full 5-day period, while the 200 m simulation ran for only 2 days due to its higher computational demand. To check the accuracy of the WRF outputs, wind data from three local meteorological stations-provided by the National Observatory of Athens [53]-were used. These stations recorded 10-minute average wind speed and main wind direction (e.g., N, NNW). The stations were located on the islands of Aegina and Salamina (within the Saronic Gulf) and Hydra (just outside the Gulf). Table 3 presents the meteorological information.

Table 3: Meteorological station information.

Station Name	Longitude (o)	Latitude (o)	Altitude (m)
Aegina	23.44364	37.74813	7
Hydra	23.46674	37.35221	2
Salamina	23.48066	37.94041	5

Figure 3 shows a comparison of model outputs from the 5 km and 1 km simulations with the local station data, presented in alphabetical order.

Figure 3: Wind speed and direction from two WRF resolutions and three local meteorological stations.

The differences seen in Figure 3 are mainly due to the unique local conditions around each meteorological station, such as terrain, vegetation, or urban areas, which are not fully captured by the model grid-even at its highest resolution of 200 m. These small-scale (microscale) features can significantly affect wind patterns but are hard to represent accurately in a model [54]. In addition, the WRF model uses complex physical parameterizations to simulate atmospheric processes like radiation, convection, and boundary layer dynamics. These parameterizations come with built-in uncertainties, which can also cause differences between the

model results and real observations [14].

In Figure 4, the high-resolution 200 m WRF simulation is included for the first 48 hours of the simulation. This early period is critical, as the effectiveness of emergency response actions taken within the first two days can greatly influence the overall success of recovery efforts and help minimize long-term environmental damage from the spill [55]. The results show very good agreement between the WRF simulations and the observational data-both in terms of pattern behavior and actual values-demonstrating the model's reliability during this crucial initial response window.

Figure 4: Wind speed and direction from three WRF resolutions and three local meteorological stations for the first 48 hours.

Finally, in Figure 5 the first 48 hours of the oil spill transport simulation is presented, showing the wind speed derived from the WRF model. This figure displays the 5km, 1km and 200m wind speed WRF, along with the trajectories of the oil particles.

Figure 5: Oil spill trajectories influenced by wind drift using WRF simulations at different resolutions: (a) 5 km, (b) 1 km, and (c) 200 m, during the first 48 hours of the event.

Figures 5a, 5b, and 5c show oil drift simulations using three different spatial resolutions: 5 km, 1 km, and 200 m. At 5 km resolution, the oil spread is more dispersed, with fewer active particles (blue) and more stranded ones (red), indicating a broader and less focused coastal impact. At 1 km, the active particles are more concentrated, the number of stranded particles is lower, and the drift path is narrower and better defined. At the finest 200 m resolution, the simulation shows the most concentrated drift path, the highest density of active particles, and the fewest stranded particles, reflecting the highest level of accuracy. All three use the same wind drift settings, but the results differ due to spatial resolution. Finer resolutions (1 km and 200 m) better capture local geography and ocean currents, leading to more accurate modeling of particle movement. These models are also more responsive to environmental changes, but they require more computational resources-especially the 200 m resolution. Higher

spatial resolution improves the model's ability to simulate small-scale wind and ocean features, like eddies and boundary currents, which strongly influence oil movement [56, 57]. This leads to more precise forecasts of where oil might travel and where it may reach the shore.

Impact of Biodegradation on Oil Weathering

In this section, we compare two 3D oil spill simulations: one that includes biodegradation and one that excludes it. Although biodegradation typically unfolds over a longer timescale [32], we observe some notable differences within the 5-day simulation period. The results are presented in Figure 6, which tracks the time evolution of key processes, including the total oil mass distribution (such as evaporated, dispersed, and stranded oil), changes in the oil's density and viscosity, and environmental factors like wind speed and sea surface current speed.

Figure 6: Time evolution of Open Oil model results (a) with biodegradation and (b) without biodegradation.

A) Oil Resurfacing: One of the first noticeable effects is that as wind speed increases after about 28 hours from the oil spill release, a significant portion of the submerged oil resurfaces. This resurfacing is a result of increased turbulence and wave entrainment, which alters the buoyancy and rise velocity of the oil droplets, pushing them back to the surface.

B) Oil Stranding: By the 80-hour mark, the amount of oil stranded on the shore starts to differ between the two scenarios. In the simulation with biodegradation (Scenario a), approximately 12% of the oil mass becomes stranded. However, in the no biodegradation scenario (Scenario b), 15% of the oil is stranded

by the same time. This suggests that biodegradation plays a role in reducing the overall amount of oil that adheres to the coast. It is likely due to changes in the physical properties of the oil, such as a breakdown in the water column, which prevents it from reaching the shore.

C) Viscosity Changes (Dynamic Emulsion Viscosity): Over the course of the simulation, the viscosity of the oil changes significantly. For the first 10 hours, the viscosity remains relatively stable at a few hundred cPoise. However, after this period, the viscosity begins to rise. By 36 hours, it increases more sharply:

- In Scenario (a), the viscosity reaches approximately 30,000 cPoise.
- In Scenario (b), it is somewhat lower, around 17,500 cPoise.

This increase in viscosity, particularly in Scenario (a), is attributed to emulsification, a process that is accelerated by biodegradation. Emulsified oil is more challenging to remove from the sea surface because it becomes thicker and more resistant to dispersal. This can complicate cleanup efforts, as it may become more difficult to collect or skim the emulsified oil from the water surface [58].

D) Oil Density: Initially, the oil has a density of 835 kg/m³, but this value changes over time. Within the first 5 hours of the spill, the density increases to around 900 kg/m³, and by 48 hours, it continues to rise, reaching approximately 1012 kg/m³. These changes are a result of the oil absorbing water, which makes it denser. As the oil's density increases, it becomes more likely to sink or remain submerged, depending on its size and weathering state.

E) Environmental Forcing: The influence of the environment also plays a significant role in the oil's behavior. As the simulation

progresses, wind speeds increase, particularly after 28 hours, which contributes to the resurfacing of submerged oil. On the other hand, sea surface currents remain steady at approximately 9 cm/s, driving the horizontal movement of the oil. These forces lead to increased wave entrainment, which causes oil to remain suspended in the water longer. As the oil droplets break into smaller particles, the oil becomes more evenly dispersed, and the vertical movement of the oil is enhanced, depending on the oil's size and density. These results are closely linked to the wind and ocean currents. Wind and current turbulence modifies the wave entrainment factor (Eq. 1), leading to greater initial dispersion of oil. It also reduces the size of resurfacing oil droplets (Eq. 2), making them remain suspended longer. Additionally, turbulence influences the vertical movement of oil particles (Eq. 3), promoting their rise or fall depending on their size and density, which results in a more dynamic and dispersed distribution of oil in the water column.

The oil mass budget, broken down by physico-chemical processes throughout the simulation, is presented in Table 4. This table shows the proportion of oil mass dispersed, submerged, surface-bound, stranded, and evaporated at each 20-hour interval, with biodegradation included in the first scenario.

Table 4: Oil weathering processes with and without biodegradation.

Processes/Time (h)	20	40	60	80	100	120
With biodegradation						
Dispersed (%)	11	11	16	17	17	17
Submerged (%)	18	7	4	4	3	2
Surface (%)	17	18	14	11	10	9
Stranded (%)	2	10	12	12	13	15
Evaporated (%)	50	51	51	51	51	51
Biodegraded (%)	2	3	4	5	4	7
Without biodegradation						
Dispersed (%)	13	15	24	24	25	25
Submerged (%)	26	11	8	7	7	5
Surface (%)	27	29	21	21	18	15
Stranded (%)	2	12	14	15	17	22
Evaporated (%)	32	33	33	33	33	33

In the biodegradation scenario, Table 4 shows that 20 hours after the initial oil release, about 50% of the oil mass has evaporated, 2% has biodegraded, and 17% remains on the sea surface, not dispersed into the water column. This suggests that evaporation is a major process in the early stages following the release. As the simulation continues, around 60 hours from the release, the evaporation rate stabilizes at approximately 51%, with 4% of the oil mass biodegraded, and 16% dispersed into the water. By the end of the simulation (120 hours), the evaporation rate remains stable at 51%, the dispersed oil increases to 17%, and the biodegraded portion rises to 7%.

For the scenario without biodegradation, Table 4 shows that

after 20 hours, about 32% of the oil mass has evaporated, and 27% remains on the surface. As the simulation progresses (around 60 hours), the evaporation rate stabilizes at 33%, and 24% of the oil particles are dispersed into the water column. By 120 hours, the percentage of dispersed oil particles increases to 25%, with the amount of evaporated oil remaining constant.

The behavior of the particles under different biodegradation conditions reveals distinct patterns over time. In the biodegradation scenario, dispersed oil starts at 11% and increases gradually to 17% over 120 hours. Submerged oil decreases from 18% to 2%, indicating rapid sinking likely due to densification from biodegradation. Surface particles decrease from 17% to 9%,

possibly because biodegradation is breaking them down. Stranded particles increase from 2% to 15%, likely due to the accumulation of biodegraded oil on the shores. Evaporated oil remains consistently high at 50-51%.

In the scenario without biodegradation, dispersed oil starts higher at 13% and steadily increases to 25%, suggesting longer persistence in the water column. Submerged oil decreases gradually, indicating slower sinking. Surface particles start at 27% and decrease steadily to 15%, reflecting a slower breakdown without biodegradation. Stranded oil increases from 2% to 22%, showing a steady movement toward the shores. Evaporated oil remains stable at 32-33%.

These differences demonstrate the significant impact of biodegradation on the distribution and fate of the oil particles. Biodegradation accelerates the breakdown and movement of oil, while the absence of biodegradation results in longer persistence of the oil in the water and more accumulation on the shores.

Conclusions

This study examines the release of BRENT crude oil near Piraeus Harbor over a 5-day period, considering two main scenarios: the first involving the use of WRF and OpenOil under three spatial resolution analyses, and the second incorporating biodegradation processes.

1. Outcomes of Different Spatial Resolution Scenarios in Simulating Oil Spill Transport:

- Higher resolution models (1km and 200m) were more sensitive to environmental changes, providing more accurate simulations of oil particle movement and stranding locations.

2. Impact of Biodegradation Process:

- The biodegradation scenario showed higher oil mass evaporation rates, with around 50% of the oil evaporating within 20 hours, compared to only 32% in the scenario without biodegradation.
- Biodegradation significantly influenced the oil's fate and distribution, with 2% of the oil biodegraded in the first 20 hours, increasing to 7% by the end of the simulation (120 hours).
- In the biodegradation scenario, a larger portion of the oil remained at the sea surface during the initial hours (17%) compared to 27% in the no-biodegradation scenario.
- Over the 5-day period, the proportion of dispersed oil particles increased to 17% with biodegradation, while it reached 25% without biodegradation.
- These results highlight the significant impact of biodegradation on oil fate, influencing evaporation, dispersion, and biodegradation rates over time.

Future Work and Development:

- Simulate accidental seafloor oil spills, such as those from the Prinos oil field in the northern Aegean Sea, to evaluate the

behavior of oil spills in different environmental conditions.

- Investigate the effects of environmental factors like temperature, salinity, and nutrient availability on oil biodegradation at varying depths in marine environments.
- Explore the integration of more detailed biological processes into the biodegradation model, focusing on microbial communities and metabolic pathways involved in oil degradation.
- Study the combined effects of prolonged biodegradation and other weathering processes like evaporation and dispersion to better understand their joint impact on oil transport and fate.

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Author Contributions

V.P. conceived the study and wrote the abstract; V.P. and C.A. wrote introduction and results; D.M. prepared WRF atmospheric input data; A.M. and K.V. reviewed the first draft; A.M, K.V and I.G. supervised the methodology and conclusions sections; S.V and I.K. funding acquisition. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Available upon request.

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